

Enhancing Inhibition on Phytopathogens by Complex Using Biogas Slurry

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Abstract : Biogas slurry was mixed with six commercial fungicides and screening against 11 phytopathogens was carried out. Results showed that inhibition of biogas slurry was different for the test strains and no significant difference between treatments of *Didymella bryoniae*, *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *vasinfectum*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizoctonia cerealis*, *F. graminearum* and *Septoria tritici* was observed. However, significant differences were found among *Penicillium* sp., *Botrytis cinerea*, *Alternaria sonali*, *F. oxysporum* F. sp. *melonis* and *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*. The approach described here presents a promising alternative to current manipulation although some issues still need further examination. This study could contribute to the development of sustainable agriculture and better utilization of biogas slurry.

Keywords : anaerobic digestion, biogas slurry, phytopathogen, sustainable agriculture

Conference Title : ICABBSS 2014 : International Conference on Agro-Biotechnology, Biosafety and Seed Systems

Conference Location : Singapore, SG

Conference Dates : March 30-31, 2014